

checkCIF/PLATON report

Structure factors have been supplied for datablock(s) shelx

THIS REPORT IS FOR GUIDANCE ONLY. IF USED AS PART OF A REVIEW PROCEDURE FOR PUBLICATION, IT SHOULD NOT REPLACE THE EXPERTISE OF AN EXPERIENCED CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC REFEREE.

No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: shelx

Bond precision: C-C = 0.0060 A Wavelength=1.54184

Cell: a=13.4690(4) b=7.8954(2) c=13.6108(4)
 alpha=90 beta=112.191(4) gamma=90

Temperature: 150 K

	Calculated	Reported
Volume	1340.21(8)	1340.20(7)
Space group	P 21/c	P 21/c
Hall group	-P 2ybc	-P 2ybc
Moiety formula	C16 H30 N6 O2, 2(F6 P), 2(H2 O)	?
Sum formula	C16 H34 F12 N6 O4 P2	C16 H34 F12 N6 O4 P2
Mr	664.43	664.43
Dx, g cm-3	1.646	1.646
Z	2	2
Mu (mm-1)	2.604	2.604
F000	684.0	684.0
F000'	688.17	
h,k,lmax	16,9,16	16,9,16
Nref	2605	2458
Tmin,Tmax	0.624,0.771	0.821,1.000
Tmin'	0.566	

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.821 Tmax=1.000
AbsCorr = MULTI-SCAN

Data completeness= 0.944 Theta(max)= 70.997

R(reflections)= 0.0548(1450) wR2(reflections)= 0.1216(2458)

S = 1.106 Npar= 192

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

Alert level C

PLAT244_ALERT_4_C	Low 'Solvent' Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of	P	Check
PLAT340_ALERT_3_C	Low Bond Precision on C-C Bonds	0.006	Ang.
PLAT906_ALERT_3_C	Large K Value in the Analysis of Variance	3.259	Check
PLAT911_ALERT_3_C	Missing FCF Refl Between Thmin & STh/L= 0.600	43	Report
PLAT978_ALERT_2_C	Number C-C Bonds with Positive Residual Density.	0	Info

Alert level G

PLAT171_ALERT_4_G	The CIF-Embedded .res File Contains EADP Records	1	Report
PLAT790_ALERT_4_G	Centre of Gravity not Within Unit Cell: Resd. # F6 P	2	Note
PLAT910_ALERT_3_G	Missing # of FCF Reflection(s) Below Theta(Min).	1	Note
PLAT912_ALERT_4_G	Missing # of FCF Reflections Above STh/L= 0.600	104	Note

0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain
0 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully
5 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight
4 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

0 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data
1 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
4 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
4 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
0 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check

It is advisable to attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. In order to resolve some of the more serious problems it may be necessary to carry out additional measurements or structure refinements. However, the purpose of your study may justify the reported deviations and the more serious of these should normally be commented upon in the discussion or experimental section of a paper or in the "special_details" fields of the CIF. checkCIF was carefully designed to identify outliers and unusual parameters, but every test has its limitations and alerts that are not important in a particular case may appear. Conversely, the absence of alerts does not guarantee there are no aspects of the results needing attention. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

Publication of your CIF in IUCr journals

A basic structural check has been run on your CIF. These basic checks will be run on all CIFs submitted for publication in IUCr journals (*Acta Crystallographica*, *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation*); however, if you intend to submit to *Acta Crystallographica Section C* or *E* or *IUCrData*, you should make sure that full publication checks are run on the final version of your CIF prior to submission.

Publication of your CIF in other journals

Please refer to the *Notes for Authors* of the relevant journal for any special instructions relating to CIF submission.

PLATON version of 03/05/2019; check.def file version of 29/04/2019

